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Identification of Indicators, Metrics and Level of Service for the Resilience of Critical Transport Infrastructure

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Abstract

Today's society is becoming increasingly dynamic from the point of view of mobility, therefore ensuring the full functionality of transport networks is becoming increasingly complex. Among various approaches to tackle this challenge, the emerging concept of Resilience has been recently shown to be applicable to transport networks as well.

Adopting a resilient approach since the first phase of evaluation and planning of an infrastructure is certainly an efficient solution than to work on improving infrastructures that have not been designed with the idea of resilience in mind. However, even if an existing critical transport infrastructure has not been designed with a resilient approach, it is still possible, during the operational phase, to introduce resilient elements by means of updating risk management plans, with resilience indicators, so that to keep the same level of service the infrastructure has to provide, whilst securing the business continuity requirements.

Keywords: Resilience, Critical Infrastructure, Level of Service, Indicators, Metrics, Business Continuity.

1 INTRODUCTION

Today, the security and resilience of critical infrastructure (CI) is a priority. Therefore, there is the need to work at the development of methodologies to assess risk from current and emerging threats and of tools to support decision making for response planning to enhance the security and resilience of the CI and to mitigate environmental, economics and material damage impacts that may arise from physical and cyber threats.

In this context, CI resilience can be defined as the ability to reduce the magnitude and/or duration of destructive events. The effectiveness of a resilient infrastructure will depend upon its capacity to anticipate, absorb, adapt to, and/or rapidly recover from a potentially disruptive event.

A governance framework that ensures resilience measures are applied to multiple CI sectors is essential. However, due to their interconnected and interdependent nature, a damage to a CI would result in potential damages to other CIs and would then generate cascading effects, which make application of resilience measures across CIs even more challenging.

Today, to effectively ensure security and safety, there is the need to translate them into resilience. The years ahead will see the emerging of new risks, as those induced by climate changes. In this context, the capacity to withstand, respond rapidly and adapt to this new and emerging risks will be a key advantage for the communities that implement a resilient approach.

A strong collaboration between private and public sector will become essential to the success of this resilience model. It requires creating capabilities from the bottom of the society, including a civil engagement and volunteerism: this will influence the business activities as well, depending on the successful realization of this collaboration between private and public sector.

CI resilience from a Life-Cycle perspective, by describing the various phases and associated services from evaluation and planning to operation and maintenance. In details, for each phase, we will try to answer to the following three questions: What this phase stands for? What is the phase about? Who is responsible for what?

A critical TI is an infrastructure that due to its importance at national level, its networked characteristics and its connections with other infrastructures, if subjected to disruption, would cause relevant consequence at national level in terms of traffic interruption, services interruption and finally economic consequences.

Overlooking a resilience model means is to put in danger the future development of the countries. For example a terroristic organization sees TI as an attractive target, especially in the case they do not have the capacity to quickly recover to an attack. There are different problems that are blocking the practical application of resilient approaches in TI. Among the others the inability to monetize resilience for decision making especially in the long term and the lack of built-in resilience capability. Moreover, strong gaps in coordination, leadership and workforce capabilities create barriers to the implementation of resilience. There is uncertainty about cross-borders issues and risks resulting from a major system disruption because risks are not well understood. All these cause that in a control center, when emergency occurs, the decision makers are overloaded by information and thus the reaction to an event might be jeopardized. There is a clear need of developing innovative solutions to increase situation awareness before, during and after emergencies. To make this happens it is essential to increase the understanding of the risks associated to human accidents, natural and extreme events. Regulatory guidance and operational procedures are examples of means and way to make resilience operational by policy.

To this end, one needs first to provide a baseline definition of resilience, of resilience indexes and level of services and resilience measures and integrating them in governance mechanisms. Beyond technical objectives it is necessary that socioeconomic objectives are well understood to help stakeholders in increase the awareness on resilience. Essentially, the goal of an infrastructure manager is to guarantee business continuity on the one hand and get revenues on the other hand.

In terms of governance the introduction of a resilience framework could lead the operator of a TI not to perform activities only when they are required by law (e.g. maintenance to be performed every year), but when there is a need as preventive action to anticipate problems or issues that might arise. It could happen that the application of a resilient model leads the operator to increase the costs of the tools (for highway) or access charges (for railway), but these additional costs would be justified by providing a Level of Service (LoS) that guarantee resilience against adverse events, thus finally returning in a benefit for the collectivity.

Once benefits of resilience are understand, then procedures and policies have to be put in place to encourage investments, in front of incentives and a benefit that are shared across the stakeholders, the users and the community. Realistic investment should have the following objectives:

- To maintain the business continuity;
- To develop means to overcome graceful degradation of function when an infrastructure is under stress;
- To contribute to quickly recover to a desired level of functionality.

We examine Metrics and Indicators and LoS that are applicable to Critical Transport Infrastructure, starting from a literature review and making them tangible in terms of potential application and use:

- A metric can be defined as a system of related measuring enabling quantification of some characteristic of a system, component or process and is composed of two or more measures. The metric represents incident rate, which is related to the “security attribute of a system, in function of time. Metrics are by nature quantifiable, therefore, in general terms, qualitative measures cannot be used as metrics. However, when dealing with topics such as Information Technology (IT), qualitative measures are also used as metrics, due to the fact that certain aspects of IT are not easily quantified.
- The Resilience Indicators (RIs) can be qualitative or quantitative. They are qualitative if they provide an information about an item of concern. These types of indicators may be most appropriate considering the quality of infrastructures management (e.g. operation maintenance) or when assessing stakeholder’s interaction with infrastructures. They are quantitative if they provide appropriate technical feature of infrastructures (e.g. year of bridge constructed, annual temperature etc.) and, when this information are not available, one can make use of data from monitoring campaign or binary indicators. These last have a yes or no answer. Some climate adaptation indicator could be binary indicators.
- The level of service (LoS) is a qualitative measure used to relate the infrastructure operability and describe how change the functionality of IC in case of an event. Infrastructures are interconnected: an event could trigger a cascading effect. Beyond the hypothetical events, ICs shall take into account the rare, unique and unplanned event that bring serious repercussion on the CI. This type of events extends the interruption of the service to be provided by the CI and therefore has a negative impact on the LoS, since it makes more difficult the return at normal operation.

2 THE CONCEPT OF RESILIENCE AND ITS ADOPTION IN CRITICAL INFRASTRUCTURE SYSTEMS:

2.1 RESILIENCE

Resilience means “bounce” [P. Stefanato, 2018]. The concept of resilience derives from physics, intended as the material ability to withstand mechanical stress. A very fragile material indicates a lower resilience, whilst a tough material presents a higher resilience. The United Nations (UN) has defined Resilience as “the ability of a system, community or society exposed to hazards to resist, absorb, accommodate to and recover from the effects of a hazard in a timely and efficient manner, including through the preservation and restoration of its essential basic structures and functions” [UNISDR, WMO, 2015].

More definitions are nowadays available, applied to different contexts and sectors. Indeed, references to resilience can be found in almost all research programs while the concept attracts the interest of social scientists, technology developers, risk managers, operational and academic researchers, engineers, etc. Some of them argue that resilience is part of disaster risk management, whereas others link most of the resilience perspectives to crisis management activities, hence to post-disaster situations, etc. Additional confusion results from the fact that in many cases resilience is seen as a built-in feature of systems and societies that can be planted to engineered infrastructures by retrofitting technology or by design, whilst on the other hand others refer to it as a strategic concept or a masterplan element that can be applied in order to reach comprehensive security for socio-technical systems.

Moreover, if we look back at the meaning of the word “Resilience”, it derives from the latin word “resilio”, which means “go back”, with particular reference to the connotation of the gesture of getting on the boat upside down by the force on the sea [R. Rancan, 2018]. This approach is still actual: indeed, the society and its citizens have the need to increase the understanding of the general risk because there is not enough perception and awareness. They have to be proactive rather than reactive, they should aim at preventing the effects, rather than repairing them.

Today, to effectively ensure security and safety, there is the need to translate them into resilience. The years ahead will see the emerging of new risks, as those induced by climate changes. In this context, the capacity to withstand, respond rapidly and adapt to this new and emerging risks will be a key advantage for the communities that implement a resilient approach. A key factor for succeeding in this is a strong collaboration between private and public sectors. It would require creating capabilities from the bottom of the society, including civil engagement this will influence the business activities as well, depending on the successful realization of this collaboration between private and public sector.

Beyond the use of the term in various applications and for various scopes, in what follows we will associate it to Critical Infrastructure (CI) – and specifically to transport ones - and we will define what does it means (applied to CI) and how a Critical Infrastructure can be defined as “resilient”.

2.2 CRITICAL INFRASTRUCTURE RESILIENCE

In 2006 the European Council and European Commission promulgated the directive EU COM (2006) 786 that obliged all Member States to adopt the components of the European Programme for Critical Infrastructure Protection (EPCIP) into their national statutes.

According to EU COM (2006) 786, a Critical Infrastructure (CI) is an asset or system essential for the maintenance of vital societal functions. Damage to CI, their destruction or disruption by natural disasters, terrorism, criminal activity or malicious behavior, has a significant negative impact on the security of our society and the well-being of its citizens.

It is widely accepted to identify as CI sectors the followings: communications, public health services, food production, banking and transport systems, governmental facilities, utilities and networks (e.g. energy) and space infrastructures (e.g. the European Copernicus and GALILEO infrastructure). Disruption to any of these sectors will cause the interruption/unavailability of services of public interest with repercussion at large scale at national or even trans-national level.

Today, the security and resilience of CI is a priority. Therefore, there is the need to work at the development of methodologies to assess risk from current and emerging threats and of tools to support decision making for response planning to enhance the security and resilience of the CI and to mitigate environmental, economics and material damage impacts that may arise from physical and cyber threats.

In this context, CI resilience can be defined as “the ability to reduce the magnitude and/or duration of destructive events. The effectiveness of a resilient infrastructure will depend upon its capacity to anticipate, absorb, adapt to, and/or rapidly recover from a potentially disruptive event”. [AIIC, 2016]

A governance framework that ensures resilience measures are applied to multiple CI sectors is essential [OECD, 2018]. However, due to their interconnected and interdependent nature, a damage to a CI would result in potential damages to other CIs and would then generate cascading effects, which make application of resilience measures across CIs even more challenging.

The resilience is a complementary attribute that uses strategies of adaptation and mitigation to improve traditional risk management. Indeed, given a certain event, the customization of Resilience within the Disaster Risk Management Cycle is depicted below [C. Fuggini, F. Bolletta, 2019], where the proper elements of resilience are integrated into or added to the phases (prevention, preparedness, response and recovery) of the Disaster Risk Management Cycle, therefore defining an infinite or panarchy loop [D. Wahl, 2017]. This is already an operationalization of early panarchy sustainable system concepts of Gunderson & Holling (2001). Looking below, Resilience can be seen as the link or capability to link pre-hazards and post-hazards activities/phases moving from 1) risk assessment to 2) resilience characterization, to 3) countermeasures and mitigation actions, to 4) preparedness and planning, enabling a more effective 5) response, leading to a 6) an efficient and timely recovery, that takes into account 7) redundancy actions up to adaptation 8) (Figure 1.1)

Figure 2.1 Resilience cycle

In the next section we will focus on the issue of CI resilience from a Life-Cycle perspective, by describing the various phases and associated services from evaluation and planning to operation and maintenance. In details, for each phase, we will try to answer to the following three questions: What this phase stands for? What is the phase about? Who is responsible for what?

We will take as reference the OECD identification of phases within the lifecycle of infrastructures project [OECD]. Accordingly, 5 main phases are identified: Evaluation and Planning; Design, Construction, Normal Operations, Emergency Operations. How the panarchy loop is integrated into the Infrastructure lifecycle is depicted in the figure below.

Figure 2.2 Resilience cycle integrated into the lifecycle of an infrastructure project

2.2.1 Phase 1: Evaluation and Planning

This first phase evaluates what are the relevant needs and requirements for an infrastructure project. To this end a Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) is provided to understand if the project is profitable for the community both in terms of costs and benefits.

Once this is assessed, the risks associated to the implementation of the project are identified, being of financial, technical and socio-political nature. This allows identifying the vulnerabilities of the infrastructure, that change based on the “context” (i.e. the location and geopolitical implications).

With this information, the risk management plan is produced so that the investor (e.g. a financial institution, a donor, etc.), can undertake its evaluation (often with the support of consultants) and then decide to finance or not the investment for the project. In this first phase it is possible to operate on time to make design changes and think about resilience strategies that can be used to face future crisis.

2.2.2 Phase 2: Design

The design phase is usually carried by external technical studies or directly by infrastructure management that design directly the project, thus lowering the design costs.

2.2.3 Phase 3: Construction

Usually this phase is attributed via tendering processes to construction companies: they are responsible for the work, whilst the supervision is attributed to the infrastructure manager. At this stage, on the contrary to the design stage, it is not possible or very difficult (and expensive) to apply structural changes. In this phase, it should be in the interest of the constructor to build a resilient infrastructure, according to the design principles, otherwise there is the risk for the constructor to increase the costs to become resilient at a later stage.

2.2.4 Phase 4: Normal Operations

This is the phase where the infrastructure is in operation. Here an adequate maintenance plan is needed for an appropriate monitoring of the asset, so that to intervene when/if needed and to save money in case an event occurs. In this phase it is important to analyze the evolutionary scenarios to identify any implementations needed to the crisis management system. In this sense it is recommended to carry out exercises for real scenarios and train the staff to them. Moreover, it is essential to periodically update the procedures and tools to implement organizational

and technological changes and maintain a readiness status of the company structures to be activated in crisis conditions.

2.2.5 Phase 5: Emergency Operations

This phase can be seen as the one that “test” or “validate” all previous phases. Indeed, if the previous phases are not correctly delivered, nor emergency plans and procedures are tested and known, it is likely that the emergency won't be tackled properly. Stress tests to the emergency operations phase can be made, by assessing the level of maturity of the organization (in this case the infrastructure manager) in terms of:

- Prevention, a collection of information of risk analysis, adoption of measures to limit crisis impact etc.;
- Preparedness, interaction of information that can enhance evaluation capabilities risk of different nature and importance;
- Response, coordination phase to help the local inter-organizational. The information coming from remote sources.

In other terms, in the case that a resilient approach is implemented, this means that Risk Management, Crisis Management and Business Continuity are parts of the same model of operation, where the first two elements serve to develop a business continuity to assure a continued infrastructure operability. As shown from the previous figure, from business continuity to risk management there is a back loop since there can be an update and thus restart the process from the beginning. Usually an emergency is triggered by an event, i.e. an incident, being an intentional or not-intentional event, able to damage people or infrastructure's assets, including the environment and the reputation of the infrastructure operator.

Emergency is the first alert state after an incident. In this phase it is carried out the first response and corporate measures are implemented to mitigate the potential damage, in cooperation and coordination with all actors involved in rescue operations.

Crisis is an exceptional event that occurs in a later stage and it can deal with objectives and infrastructure operator missions. Generally, crisis is distinguished in incapacity incident management procedures and in extraordinary resources need (e.g. extra budget).

3 RESILIENCE METRICS, INDICATORS AND LEVEL OF SERVICE FOR CRITICAL TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE

A Transport Critical Infrastructure (TCI) is an infrastructure that due to its importance at national level, its networked characteristics and its connections with other infrastructures, if subjected to disruption, would cause relevant consequences at national level in terms of traffic interruption, services interruption and finally economic consequences. According to the U.S. Department of Homeland Security the followings are the main sectors within TI [HSD site USA]: Aviation Infrastructure, including airports and air traffic control system; Maritime Infrastructure, including ports and inland water facilities; Highways, consists in bridge, tunnel and traffic management system; Pipeline Systems, including compression station and pumping station and carrying natural gas and various chemicals material; Mass Transit and Passenger Rail systems, including support infrastructure for passenger service, terminals and operations systems; Postal and Shipping services, consisting in mail services, courier services, chartered and delivery services and mail management firms; Freight Rail and logistic infrastructure.

Overlooking a resilience model means to put in danger the future development of the countries. For example, a terroristic organization sees TCI as an attractive target, especially in the case they do not have the capacity to quickly recover to an attack.

A metric can be defined as “a system of related measuring enabling quantification of some characteristic of a system, component or process and is composed of two or more measures. The metric represents incident rate, which is related to the security attribute of a system, in function of time” [ENISA, 2011]. Metrics are by nature quantifiable, therefore, in general terms, qualitative measures cannot be used as metrics. However, when dealing with topics such as Information Technology (IT), qualitative measures are also used as metrics, due to the fact that certain aspects of IT are not easily quantified” [EU-CIRCLE, 2015]. On the other hand, the indicator is different from a metric, because the value of an indicator is calculated and not measured. Indeed, the metric defines how to calculate an indicator, scored on a point scale (e.g. 1-10 or very high – very low).

The Resilience Indicators (RIs) can be qualitative or quantitative. They are qualitative if they provide an information about an item of concern. These types of indicators may be most appropriate considering the quality of infrastructures management (e.g. operation maintenance) or when assessing stakeholder's interaction with infrastructures. They are quantitative if they provide appropriate technical feature of infrastructures (e.g. year of bridge constructed, annual temperature etc.) and, when this information are not available, one can make use of data from monitoring campaign or binary indicators. These last have a yes or no answer. Some climate adaptation indicator could be binary indicators.

In what follows, the literature context for RIs is derived from the H2020 EU Project EU-CIRCLE [EU-CIRCLE], that takes into consideration five types of parameters (anticipation, absorption, coping, restoration, adaptation) and associate to each parameters some indicators.

- **Anticipation:** it includes a probability of failure that is an estimation of the expected impact and degradation of an infrastructure following a disturbance or shock. The quality of infrastructure indicates the performance and is influenced by materials, design, age, quality of maintenance. Learnability is the ability of organization to use the lessons of their own and others experience to better manage the prevailing circumstances. In crisis, when the emergency communications are high functionality, their deployment in case of crisis determinate a limit loss of functionality and speed the recovery of infrastructure function. The quality of mitigating features is a capacity of infrastructure to mitigate a shock episode; is an indicator that add quality and robustness to an infrastructure. Pre event functionality of the infrastructure is an indicator for knowing the baseline level of functionality of CI to assessing and quantifying functionally change both in normal operation case but especially after critical event. Another anticipation indicator is the quality of disturbance planning, for value pre-determined policies that maintain the functionality of the CI;
- **Absorption:** it considers the system failure and its severity; depending on characteristic of the CI and its relationship to the disturbance, an old CI could be more dangerous that a new, an event could cause persistent damage. Post event functionality indicator measures the functionality of a CI following a shock; in relation to a consequential disturbance: the closer the level of post event functionality to the assessed pre event functionality the more likely the CI is to be resilient. Resistance and robustness are two indicators that describe the quality and performance of the materials. Resistance have the objective to prevent damage or disruption and robustness is the ability to maintain critical operations and functions in the face of crisis;
- **Coping:** it evaluates the withstanding, otherwise ability, to sustain the damage; the redundancy, otherwise availably of alternative parts of the network in the event of disruption to ensure continuity of service; resourcefulness describes the capacity to skillfully prepare for manage a crisis and comprises the phases taken prior to an event to prepare workers for possible threats and the application of the training once an event occurs. Post event damage assessment provided by a geographic information system that can be used in post disaster damage assessment to give a direct idea of the robustness of the CI. The last indicator of this parameter is interoperability, otherwise ability to cooperate with neighboring cities;
- **Restoration,** regarding recovery time post event, measure of time taken for a CI to be brought back to its pre event level of functionality; recovery loss ratio calculates the speed of recovery based on the severity of loss. Cost of reinstating functionality post event calculates the cost of returning CI to pre event functionality;
- **Adaptation indicators** are for instance substitutability, otherwise the possibility that the functional aspect of an infrastructure system can be replaced by back up infrastructure. Adaptability and flexibility are capacity to change while improving functionality with alternative strategies. Impact reducing availability and consequences reducing availability are a process that reducing impact of climate changes for e.g. building construction in according to climate ready standards. Economic sustainability valuates the awareness of citizen to keep the same economic level after a critical event.

In addition to the above, additional indicators could be drawn up in parallel to a Business Impact Analysis (BIA). BIA is the starting point for all contingency planning and business continuity activities. Its objective is to identify the areas or business process more vulnerable, to limit the consequences of a disastrous event, to limit the possibility of incurring events that block service performance and return to ordinary level as soon as possible. BIA

raises a basic question: “If an event happens, the consequences would be acceptable? If no what to do?”.

It is an Infrastructure Manager (IM) task to pursue such analysis, that will be used as a measure to verify resilience. Said this and looking back at the two ways the EU-CIRCLE project and the work done by other research entities, such as the ETH in Zurich, one can conceive an hybrid approach, that takes into account both the scientific rigor of EU-CIRCLE, both the more pragmatic approach of ETH.

The figure below tries to provide a graphical representation of this union.

Figure 3.1: Graphical representation of Resilience

The level of service (LoS) is a qualitative measure used to relate the infrastructure operability and describe how change the functionality of IC in case of an event.

Infrastructures are interconnected: an event could trigger a cascading effect. Beyond the hypothetical events, IMs shall take into account the rare, unique and unplanned event that bring serious repercussion on the TCI. This type of events extends the interruption of the service to be provided by the TCI and therefore has a negative impact on the LoS, since it makes more difficult the return at normal operation.

The point 1 depicts what happens when the infrastructure endures a critical event. This is the first phase of emergency, immediately after an accident. This could cause a traffic block to allow the rescue operations, typically lasting just a few hours. Here one could implement measures of first response and crisis management as identified in the planning phase.

The point 2 depicts the start of the recovery phase; after the first hours devoted to the rescue operations, countermeasure are implemented to avoid the infrastructure collapse. If this point is very far from point 1, the system is not resilient, and the resilient area will be very wide. If the recovery plan or business continuity plan start in a short time, the restoration phase will be short term.

The point 3 depicts the procedures in place to re-establish normal operating conditions as soon as possible. All the procedures that are of concern in this phase have to be planned before an event. A fast return at normal operation depends on various resilience indicator, as identified in the planning phase.

The point 4 depicts a normal operation phase: sometimes may be the case that the return to normal operation is better than before the event happened. That is because IMs must learn from previous errors, to increase efficiency.

4 CONSIDERATIONS ON THE APPLICABILITY TO REALISTIC SCENARIOS

A very relevant and interesting example on what resilience means in practice has been provided by the case of the I-35W bridge of Minneapolis (Minnesota – USA) that collapsed into the Mississippi River on August 1 2007, causing 13 deaths. It was a 40 years old bridge, carrying 140000 vehicles daily through the center of Minneapolis. The bridge had undergone annual inspections since 1993 by the Minnesota Department of Transportation and last inspection completed in June 2006 indicated a fatigue problem. At the time of collapse, the bridge was being repaired and moreover there was construction equipment on the bridge that have contributed at its collapse. The National Transport Safety Board (NTSB) determined that the probable cause of the collapse was due to the inadequate load capacity, under-sizes compared to the traffic extent. The TCI in this case was redundant because, the bridge had an adjacent one and through this it was possible cross the river without difficulties, even in the case of the first bridge collapse. Despite this, that at least provided a business continuity, the IM could have adopted a more resilient approach that would have saved the bridge and more importantly lives, by operating periodically predictive maintenance analyses. In fact, with a periodic monitoring, it is possible to keep under control the health of structural components exposed to risks, so that to predict, on the basis of the information available, well in advance, the remaining time before a damage occurs. This approach is definitely cheaper than massive interventions and above all then intervening when the damage has been already occurred. Moreover, if predictive maintenance analysis is carried out supported by monitoring systems in place, it is essential to have in-field control centers, that manage and record all maintenance activity for a correct management of the infrastructure locally. With a normal control of maintenance work, IM should have been watching construction equipment stock on the bridge.

Despite the example provided below, it is obvious that disruptions to Transport Critical Infrastructure (TCI) are costly [Fuggini, Bolletta]. In Europe for instance, the total costs because of extreme weather events on the transport system have been estimated in €2.5 billion/year. Of these costs, about 72% are attributed to roads, 14% to air travel, and 12% to the rail sector, whilst the remaining percentages are related, in descending order of magnitude, to maritime transport, inland waterways, and intermodal freight transport [Enei et al. 2011]. Looking at the next four decades in Europe, it is expected that the road transport costs due to the effects of extreme weather events could increase by 7% [Doll, Klug, and Enei 2014]. Moreover, higher flood risks and less predictable winters could increase rail traffic costs by up to 80%.

Worldwide, baseline investment needs for TCI — with current resilience standards — could range from \$157 billion to \$1.1 trillion a year between 2015 and 2030 worldwide. The exact value would depend on the choice of mode (such as personal cars versus public transit in cities) and on the policies put in place to encourage switching to rail and public transport. In addition, between \$550 billion and \$700 billion would be needed every year to maintain the existing and new transport infrastructure in low- and middle-income countries by 2030, bringing the total annual spending needs to between \$700 billion and \$1.8 trillion.

More in details, the incremental cost of making new exposed TCI more resilient to floods and landslides lies between \$860 million and \$35 billion. This is a 0.6% increase in cost, on average, across the spending range and potentially a 5 percent increase in the most expensive case. These investments would reduce the risk of damage for new infrastructure by a factor of two. According to [Koks et al. 2019], these investments would pay for themselves through the lower repair costs for about 60 percent of roads exposed to a 1/100-year flood event (4.5 percent of the network).

CONCLUSIONS

If we start from the meaning of Critical Infrastructure (CI), an infrastructure that due to its strategical importance and functions must remain functional in all situation, we can say that this perfectly fits with the concept of resilience, the ability of an infrastructure to absorb a crisis and return at the operational state in the shortest possible time. Considering the life-cycle phases of an infrastructure, a resilient approach can be potentially applied in each phase, but in the initial ones (i.e. evaluation and planning) and during the emergency phase, since here the benefits can be exploited and maximized and the costs for implementing resilient measures are lower.

However, until now, resilience concepts have found difficulties in being adopted. Indeed, it is difficult to monetize resilience for long-term decision-making process and managers have not completely adopted this concept in their work culture. It is possible to introduce this concept together with the much more known one of the Business

Continuity (BC), as result of a proper risk management approach, so that an infrastructure is ready and operative in case of dangerous events. Concerning indicators, many of them exist in literature, but in order to adopt a resilient approach it is necessary to establish which of these are the most suitable and can be implemented into practice. To do this, working in parallel to the business impact analysis would help a lot.

Indeed, when it comes to operation, it is worth noticing that the Infrastructure Managers (IMs) are generally interested to guarantee business continuity and revenues from their business. The resilient approach would help them for example to perform maintenance not only when required by legislation, but when there is a real need and as a preventive action, opting for a more intelligence choice of using available financial resources.

Moreover, it is very important to improve the role of communication in ordinary situation, updating the operational structure of civil protection and emergency management services establishing a more correct communication flow, leaving the IMs to operate their institutional tasks, to guarantee operational continuity, rather than to coordinate emergency tasks. In this sense preliminary agreed contracts with providers of emergency services represent an element to achieve resilience during the emergency phase.

Finally, an example is provided to demonstrate the importance of resilience in infrastructure and operational planning. Spending millions of euros to overcome crisis and disaster that lead to the collapse of a TCI and a number of losses and victims, it is not the solution not for the Infrastructure Manager, neither for the transport users nor for the society overall. The alternative could be to invest in the adoption of a resilient approach. However, to make this happen, the awareness on the concept and the sensibility of IMs has to be increased, since they often lack of a proper understanding on the impacts and benefits. In this context, finding the right correlations among Business Continuity (BC) plans and resilience plans, would help a lot.

On the basis of these results and observations, the next steps of the work presented in this paper are in the direction defining suitable Business Cases that conceptualize a model of risk management strongly resilient to the context in which it is made operationally, and to finally identifying how to apply it in practice.

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